

IAU Symposium #385 “Astronomy and Satellite Constellations: Pathways Forward”

Connie Walker

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The [IAU Symposium #385](#) (IAUS385) “Astronomy and Satellite Constellations: Pathways Forward” took place 2–6 October 2023 in La Palma, Canary Islands. Connie Walker, Head of the Office of Site Protection at NSF’s NOIRLab and Co-Director of the [IAU Centre for the Protection of the Dark and Quiet Sky from Satellite Constellation Interference](#), chaired the Scientific Organizing Committee for this event.

The symposium was a huge success, and the IAU CPS was heavily involved with the preparation of the [sessions](#). The CPS Hubs who attended in person were [SatHub](#) co-leads Siegfried Eggel (University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign) and Mike Peel (Imperial College London); [Policy Hub](#) co-leads Richard Green (University of Arizona) and Andrew Williams (ESO); [Community Engagement Hub](#) co-lead Jessica Heim (University of Southern Queensland); and [Industry and Technology Hub](#) co-lead Tim Stevenson (SKAO).

The SatHub sessions concentrated on challenges to radio and optical astronomy, spectroscopy, space-based observations, and amateur astronomy. They also addressed strategies for co-existence in these categories, including the various approaches developed in recent years in optical

astronomy. There are now better models and data for satellite brightness, which are key to enabling any sort of mitigation, for active avoidance, and for use in compliance checks. Future observations by the CPS SatHub observing network will determine whether some coatings and [Bragg mirrors](#) on reflective surfaces of Starlink satellites will help, and if so how well. For spectroscopy, better modeling and understanding of satellite spectra will enable satellite emissions to be calibrated out of astronomical data. Autonomous imagers on large spectroscopic facilities can help identify when an exposure was contaminated. For space-based observatories there are software solutions (Starunlink) for streak detection and elimination that may be helpful. Ultimately SatHub is bringing all stakeholders together to tackle the impact of satellite constellations on astronomy.

The Policy Hub sessions focused on ways to raise awareness and encourage coordination. The Policy Hub is engaging a growing network of ~140 people in research and policy work conducting regular interactions with government affairs representatives from several national astronomical societies, observatories, and spectrum managers. These sessions also included discussions on deliverables from the

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work packages the Policy Hub has undertaken (a position paper, Space Sustainability Rating, consolidating recommendations from the SATCON-related workshops [[SATCON1](#), [SATCON2](#)], lunar policy, etc.).

The Community Engagement Hub aims at the establishment of a fair-minded forum for the conscious and respectful discussion of satellite constellations with all stakeholders involved and communities affected, especially communities outside of professional astronomy. Toward this goal, the Community Engagement sessions at IAUS385 included presentations from Elder Wilfred Buck and other traditional knowledge keepers. The speakers shared perspectives on their relationship with the sky and cosmos and discussed ways to co-create collaborative endeavors related to the night sky and space. Speakers with a background in history and science and technology studies explored past and present space and astronomy issues from different lenses and the environmental and cultural aspects of these topics.

The Industry and Technology Hub session panel included a representative from SpaceX, who provided an update on Starlink satellites and their mitigation measures. The Q&A highlighted a number of concerns regarding relationships

with regulators, the state of the market and limits to it, and the flow of information from operators to support independent researchers.

Progress in policymaking in countries throughout the world was also highlighted at the symposium. The general message conveyed was that steady interaction with policymakers and industry is required to raise awareness and promote the protection of dark and quiet skies. There are a growing number of high-level entities who have recognized the importance of dark and quiet skies, including the [European Council](#), [ESA Clean Space Charter](#), [G7](#), [Earth Space Sustainability Initiative](#), and [UN Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space \(COPUOS\)](#).

Next steps for the IAU CPS include examining the information presented at the symposium, developing collaborations on the topics addressed at the symposium, and encouraging individuals to join the IAU CPS.

My presentation to the National Academies of Science, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM) Committee on Astronomy and Astrophysics Fall 2023 Meeting summarizing IAUS385 is available on the NASEM website.